

Management

ROLE OF E-LEARNING IN ACHIEVING TOTAL QUALITY (THE CASE OF IRAQI UNIVERSITIES)

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Abstract

Over the past years, TQM has achieved remarkable and remarkable successes in many international organizations as a model, method and strategy in the field of business management in organizations and institutions in general. Hence, business strategies and management cannot be far from TQM in its methodology and strategy but both match a goal and a method. The application of TQM as an integrated approach and strategy is the primary guarantee of achieving competitive advantage in the activities of the basic organizations and their survival and continuity in the market in light of globalization and its repercussions.

Keywords: E-learning; Total Quality Management; Universities.

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1. Introduction

In the universities, TQM is not only a management philosophy adopted and implemented by the university departments, but it has become the integrated approach and strategy which has its components and its elements which have taken a lot, achieving remarkable results in the application when it became a strategic priority that corresponds to its comprehensive and integrated strategies. Is still in place, especially in the field of distance learning and e-learning, in which the recipient should be prepared to achieve the goals of the relevant websites. Iraqi universities being among the system of developing countries have to walk in the overall quality through several means, in particular the development of e-learning. It is one of the factors of success in linking the vision of the organization's mission at the strategic level and because the educational system now faces a challenge regarding the need to provide additional educational opportunities without the need to increase additional budgets, I began to face this challenge by developing and implementing distance education and e-learning programs.

Research Goals

The aim of this research is to highlight TQM in the university as a whole, as well as in the field of e-learning. It is worth noting that considerable efforts have been made in the exposure to TQM as well as in the field of e-learning, overall in e-learning was small, so it would be useful to address this, and may be of interest to those interested.

Research Methodology

The methodology of the research, in the descriptive presentation and analysis, has imposed this division of study into a number of disciplines, which were to clarify the concepts related to TQM, then e-learning, related contents and related strategies.

Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis of the research is that the entrance to e-learning is necessary in the context of access to TQM in the management of universities in general because these guarantees the proper performance and increase the competitiveness of the university in general and Iraq in particular.

The First Topic: The Concept of TQM

The TQM concept has emerged as a comprehensive term, demonstrating the process of quality improvement. The concept of TQM has become an important managerial method in the management of organizations through the success of this new method of management success, which includes a description of the production processes and proposed amendments that help to improve quality continuously.

TQM is an integrated management approach, consisting of many aspects that must be applied in a holistic manner and under favorable internal conditions. Therefore, the philosophy of TQM encompasses two concepts: totalitarian and integrative. The overall expansion of the quality of services expected by customers, outlook. Integrity refers to the fact that an enterprise as a system of subsystems depends on one another. From this perspective, TQM includes the process of horizontal integration between departments and departments in order to improve the quality of service and the quality of the administrative system.

This philosophy requires full cooperation between all departments and departments at all levels of management, direct supervision of all elements of administrative levels and direct supervision of all operational elements, including administrative, financial, procurement and finally the service itself.

A fundamental requirement for the application of the TQM philosophy is that administrative leadership has the willingness to change the organizational behavior of team members, and the ability to define their roles and clarify the results of applying this philosophy.

The management can change organizational behavior in the organization by changing how individuals perform business (preventing problems rather than problem solving, as well as using teams instead of competing departments). Managers also have to shift from heads to leaders. Employees should create instead so we see that all these requirements are the responsibility of management, as it is concerned with establishing the organizational culture of the enterprise, and thus it can be said that TQM can be applied only by senior management. There are those who

believe that TQM begins with the commitment of senior management to quality and participation in the pursuit of it. Without substantive support from this top management, quality will not be a slogan.

Researchers and writers disagree about a specific definition of TQM but agree on some aspects of this concept. These definitions include:

Mr. Murad Murad defines TQM as "an integrated management philosophy through which to better manage the organization by identifying the aspirations and hopes of its clients and providing services in a manner that achieves the highest possible satisfaction for them and their employees in light of the available possibilities and the surrounding circumstances.

One of the most notable definitions is the definition of Dr. Omar Wasfi Aqili as he finds it: "A modern management philosophy that takes the form of an approach or a comprehensive administrative system based on making radical changes to everything within the organization. These changes include thought, behavior, values, organizational beliefs, , Management style, work and performance systems and procedures, etc., in order to improve and develop all the components of the organization, to reach the highest quality in its outputs (goods or services) and at the lowest cost, in order to achieve the highest degree of satisfaction of its customers by satisfying their needs and desires , According to what they expect, and even exceeded this expectation, in line with Strategy recognizes that customer satisfaction and the goal of the organization are one goal, and the survival of the organization and its success and continuity depends on this satisfaction, as well as the satisfaction of all who deal with non-customers and others"

It is clear from this that TQM should be seen as an integrated approach to customer service. It is not just a specialized department that seeks to achieve quality in one or more areas within the organization, but an integrated process that includes all activities, One of which is a weak point that affects overall quality, because the chain of production chains are interrelated, and this interdependence needs high-level coordination to be achieved by a higher board or committee within the organization.

2. The Second Topic: Total Quality Management in Universities

Universities are characterized by highly qualified scientific organizations in terms of individuals, diversity of competencies and ability to develop, and they are the most productive institutions of knowledge (scientific research and consumption education.

Any organization with these characteristics must be the most qualified to adopt TQM with its different concepts and practices as follows:

First: TQM has gained wide popularity and no university can stay away from it and take it into consideration.

Second: as the economies of developed countries move from industry-based economies to services-based economies, the education sector is also becoming one of the largest areas of service.

Third: The issuance of the ISO 9000 series and a wide range of national quality standards in each country in addition to the national quality awards have made universities concerned with

this quality concern. This is why universities are increasingly looking for quality awards, and many of them are ISO certified.

Fourthly, the universities themselves are facing the challenges of intense competition between universities on the one hand and the submission of universities to the challenges of the national assessment process through accreditation standards and the global assessment of universities, as in the assessment of universities and with all this wide and diverse movement for total quality management And the ISO 9000 series, both public and private universities are at the heart of TQM and ISO 9000.

3. Total Quality Management Tools in Universities

There are many TQM tools that are used in universities and are suitable for use even in various faculties of the university, including:

- Focus on the community service in which the college is located.
- The need for planning and guidance.
- Work to ensure training and continuous education for participants in the embodiment of TQM College.
- Self-assessment of each user in college.
- Ensure participation in decisions that are of interest to the college for users.
- Leadership must be secured by the need to respect the opinion and opinion of the other.
- Work to provide and practice what is known as quality seminars in colleges and universities.
- It is essential to ensure effective communication between the faculty and the university.
- The need to adopt the method of motivation and reward for users of colleges and university with the recognition of effective performance.
- The need for cooperation between the officials of the faculties and the university as well as work to ensure the renewal and continuous improvement of the services provided.
- Work to keep pace with the rhythm and pace of competition with colleges located in other universities.
- Work to provide a system of monitoring and follow-up.
- The observance of these tools will ensure survival, continuity and stand in front of local, regional and global competition.

TQM in the universities is based on several basic rules, including:

- The basis for achieving results and good performance and improving the organizational effectiveness of colleges and universities.
- The development of the competitive center for colleges.
- The base of interaction and environmental interconnection.
- Satisfaction rule: Career for employees, students and beneficiaries of colleges. .
- Innovation and innovation base and new inventions and research colleges.
- The self-financing base and the diversity of sources of income for colleges.

The implementation of the basic rules mentioned above ensures that the university's constituent colleges will have long-term strategic planning for quality as the return of education is cumulative. The basic rules will ensure the quality of services and educational programs as well as the planning and quality control of research and advisory processes.

4. Methods of Applying Total Quality in Universities

The focus here is on defining the methods of introduction and embodiment of TQM in the universities and the various faculties of its constituents in order to reflect reforms and work on continuous development, in addition to identifying opportunities for renewal and improving the competitive location of faculties.

The application and embodiment of TQM helps to achieve all the objectives of the faculties and satisfy the needs of the students who are the beneficiaries of the faculties as well as the staff of the faculties, whether it is professors or administrators. It is important to emphasize that there are many advantages of adopting the TQM program and even seeking ISO certification. Can be identified as follows:

- This quest will lead to the adoption of an emphasis on quality
- It can open the way for universities to benefit from experiences and practices in the continuous improvement of different aspects in the various programs of the University.
- It requires fundamental changes in the university culture to be more team-oriented, teamwork and continuous improvement.

That will make evaluation and calibration very important not only in self-assessment and internal calibration but also more importantly external evaluation and competitive calibration with peers in the education sector. Perhaps these advantages explain the fact that a growing number of universities have adopted TQM programs. Despite the importance of these advantages which encourage the adoption of TQM as well as ISO certification in universities, this does not mean that the road is smooth and without obstacles. While emphasizing that the TQM program and ISO certification impose many modifications and demands, it is not easy to achieve them in a short period of time as requirements and conditions that must be met and achieved for the successful implementation of this program,

Other determinants of this adoption are related to the nature of the universities and their distinct characteristics that may conflict with one another or another with TQM programs and ISO certification.

Assessment is the identification and measurement of activities or results actually achieved and their comparison to the predetermined criteria, whether this criterion is what was achieved in the previous period or is the pre-defined standard at the level of the sector in which the administrative unit operates. , Since evaluation can include quantitative or significant indicators in quality assessment.

That the evaluation process at universities is linked to internal evaluation external evaluation. Universities that adopt quality improvement programs are not limited to internal evaluation, so this assessment is directed towards successfully passing the external evaluation process. This is

what we find, for example, in German universities that, in their quest to improve quality, have adopted internal evaluation based on the quality plan.

The growing demand for university education may have a negative impact on maintaining this lower quality of attention. The main objective of accreditation is to maintain the quality of educational programs. And because many of the indicators related to accreditation may be total (as in 45 students / professors). The level of systematic self-assessment, which is characterized by an internal quality assurance plan for the university administration, is then evaluated to evaluate their systems, curricula and academic and research programs. This plan is the first improvement base in order to remedy any imbalance at the expense of public accreditation and to improve it in order to achieve the highest level, which can be in the overlap and participation with prestigious universities and accept the process of assessing quality assurance in universities seeking to develop its quality assurance program. Followed by the international level of ISO certification (9000-2000) based on the integrated system of total quality management. To come after it aspiration university to be in the ranking of universities in the world. Finally, at the top of this runway ranking of the world's top ten universities, each of which is suitable to be an international benchmark in this area.

The university is a large educational research institution that activities multi-processes and thus multi-output systems and results. Because TQM (as well as ISO 9000) is comprehensive for the entire university, so the components of the evaluation program must be a comprehensive framework for the entire university. (5) Criteria or elements of accreditation (mission and integrity, preparation for the future, access, discovery and application of knowledge, attention and service). While the requirements for accreditation at a university such as the University of Colorado (Colorado) up to (24) requirement. The New England Association of Schools and Colleges (NEAS & C) has identified 11 criteria or elements for accreditation in higher education institutions:

- Mission and purpose of the institution and its integrity in accordance with ethical standards and transparency.
- Planning and evaluation of the institution.
- Organization and governance of the institution.
- Academic program of the institution.
- College qualifications (resources, teaching methods, facilities
- Students (admission criteria, college assessment methods, methods of measuring their success, student services, etc
- Sources and information technology in the institution.
- Material and technological resources in the enterprise.

The comprehensive university quality model must include the basic components required, including:

FIRST: Strategic Quality This is what can be called directors creators, which refers to what became known as strategic assets in the institution and the university, which include: a vision, a message, the purpose of the University and the main trends that distinguish them from others. This component is effective whenever the university has clear and specific answers to the following:

- The image of the future university and its development prospects and competitiveness.
- University focus: education or scientific research or both.
- The services that it seeks to offer to customers started with students and suppliers (secondary schools) and beneficiaries (companies) to the community as a whole.

SECOND: Value Creation the types of university services include:

- Research processes, projects and experiments
- Consulting processes
- Training processes related to the provision of training activity in its various forms
- Innovative processes: whether in the field of education or in the field of research as in distinguished research, patent registration, innovation of concepts and scientific theories
- Sharing resources, talents, and experiences, thus maintaining individual excellence.

THIRD: Enables factors: representing the creation of value in the university, these factors are:

- Information technology and associated.
- Financial and material resources: from the potential and financial allocations for the development of buildings, halls, laboratories, workshops, teaching methods, scientific experimentation, publishing, writing and others.
- Connectivity: Utilization of Intranet, Extranet and Internet services, and subscription to databases, data repositories and electronic publishing.
- Scientific and administrative: such as promotion systems and scientific work and support scientific publication that stimulates scientific academic production as well as flexible administrative systems and incentive systems for scientific and administrative owners.

FOURTH: Relationships: Relationships are one of the basic assets of the intellectual capital of the university, which is related to the stakeholders. The parties to the relationship with the university are:

- Students.
- Research, consulting and training centers outside the university.
- Other universities.
- Media libraries and publishing houses.
- Secondary schools
- Related scientific societies.

FIFTH: Results: The results are the measure that shows the university's status among the universities and the achievement of success or failure to achieve its objectives in relation to the creation of value and relationships these include the results:

- Location of universities in national, regional and international assessments
- The University's partnerships with prestigious universities and general accreditation at the professional level, national, regional and international.
- Prestigious scientific awards obtained by the university or scientific owners.
- The university obtains a certificate or certificate of excellence in university quality, including the ISO certificate.
- Scientific research published in national or international journals.
- Scientific authorship of methodological books and assistance.

- The size and quality of the consultancy offered by the university.
- The size and diversity of training programs organized by the university.
- The scientific journal of the University and the regularity of its issuance and the extent of recognition.
- The University's ability to attract distinguished professors.
- Scientific conferences and the size and quality of participation in them.
- University's reputation in society.

5. The Third Topic: E-Learning and Distance Learning

One of the facts is that if the Internet had not existed, electronic activities would not have existed or would have become as advanced and influential in business. In order to effectively deal with the Internet in the field of business and e-commerce, it requires the support of information systems in order to give the activity required to achieve. There is no doubt that the methods and methods of handling and managing data have been a natural extension of the progress of MIS in the last quarter of the last century. It is now possible to present data and information and make any changes to the decision-makers in order to serve the communication process between the two sides of the process. The fundamental idea is that the Internet is an effective tool for transferring information between interacting parties in e-business. And therefore its use will reflect positively on the organization and in achieving its objectives first and the value of the effectiveness of the information system

Used by them with other parties involved in the process. Therefore, the most prominent advantages of Internet use can be described as:

- Costs, reduced
- Flexibility and its competitive advantages
- Reduce risk
- Develop the relationship with the customer.

E-learning is the modern shift in teaching methods and techniques that use the latest technology and equipment in the education process to achieve the overall quality. It is the process of learning or receiving scientific information through the use of multimedia technologies in isolation from time and space, where contact between students and professors through many means may be the Internet or Intranet or extranet or interactive television. The process of education according to place, time, quantity and quality chosen by the learner, according to criteria to ensure that the student absorbed the curriculum and programs prepared.

6. E-Learning Or Online Study

E-learning is a means of supporting the educational process and transforming it from the stage of indoctrination to the stage of creativity, interaction and skills development, which is the correct approach to total quality.

E-learning: the use of modern electronic means of education. And many universities today provide a range of scientific disciplines within university studies without the need to be on campus. The Internet provides many open universities as a form of distance learning within the

organizational restructuring of the educational process. It is the "new educational orientation" within the philosophy of "unlimited education in time and place". The main engine for this is the Internet. Web-based learning grows and expands to take up the space it deserves in cyberspace.

7. E-Learning in Iraq

Since 2003, the higher education sector has devoted great attention to increasing the number of students admitted to universities and higher institutes based on the philosophy that there is a great shortage of high degree holders compared to the countries of the region. It does not meet the need of the market and society for scientific specialties.

In the past three years, there has been a significant expansion in the number of universities. This number has increased from (19) universities to (29), which exceeded the national strategy for education and higher education in Iraq for the years 2011 to 2000. 160 thousand students were accepted in 2013-2014 in the morning study only and an increase of 22% on the number of students admitted in 2010-2011. In addition, 96 colleges, 217 departments and 48 branches were added in Iraqi universities as well as a number of higher institutes in various technical and medical disciplines. The number of graduate students rose 56 percent in two years and the number of private colleges rose from 26 in 2010 to 39 in 2013, with more than 105,000 students. It appears that the number of students in primary studies of higher education increased from 416 thousand to 554 thousand in the third three years (an increase of 33%) and the number of graduate students from about 17 thousand to 30 thousand (up 76%), In contrast to this large rise did not increase the number

Only 23% (from about 12899 to about 15915). Unfortunately, there is no information about the improvement in the level of training and the increase of their knowledge during this period, nor the marked change in the very high proportion of teachers from local degree holders, nor On the rate of increase in equipment and electronic systems, which is expected to be accompanied by a huge increase in the number of graduate students. Although the report confirms the ministry's ability to absorb the increasing numbers of students, there is evidence to the contrary, which comes from deans and heads of departments, who assert that the ministry forces them to weaken the capacity of their colleges and departments, especially graduate students. The higher education policy emphasizes the increase in the number of admissions in universities based on comparison with the number of university students in Arab and regional countries. There is a problem in these figures because the method of calculation is vague and different methods are adopted. It is possible that the percentage of students who have a preparatory certificate and who were admitted to higher education in university, technical and vocational in a specific year or calculate the percentage of admissions in these institutions and alumni, Of the population, or by calculating the gross enrollment ratio of the total population in a particular year, or as in the Ministry's report, which was based on the calculation of the ratio of tertiary enrollment to the population aged 18-23. In some countries, the ratio is calculated as 17-30 years old.

But the actual situation taken by the curricula in the Iraqi universities during the past years completely different, as it has become the methodological book or alternative (cloned lieutenant) is the most important factor in the system of educational process in most scientific and humanitarian disciplines taught in Iraqi universities.

The most important proposals in this regard are the orientation towards e-learning programs, not as a technical luxury, but as an effective solution to many of the problems experienced by the educational process. Over the last three years, Iraqi universities have tried to engage in e-learning and have sought to provide many of the necessary supplies and tools. Most of these experiments have not yet achieved their goals. Traditional methods of education are still prevalent in all universities. As well as that many of the devices and laboratories that were equipped for the purposes of e-learning, consumed before they are invested in real. Or used for other purposes. Including at best providing Internet services, computer labs, and in other cases used for printing official books and exam questions, or lecture halls.

Hence, the employment of e-learning is necessary to achieve the overall quality in the Iraqi universities.

8. Conclusion

The current global challenges necessitate the educational organizations to adopt the scientific method conscious in the face of these challenges and to invest the human capacities in the performance of performance efficiency more efficient and effective, and the most administrative aspects aimed at TQM, which has become thanks to the huge amount of information and communication technologies is a distinctive phenomenon of dimensions of thought Modern human resources, especially since modern scientific administration has contributed extensively to the development of the structure of business organizations.

Total quality has become one of the most important principles of management at present. The development of the concepts and practices of TQM and the implementation of its programs of positive results in business organizations have been a great incentive for the implementation of these programs in the services sector, including universities. There is no doubt that there is an important role of e-learning in this regard. This study concludes:

FIRST: CONCLUSIONS

Universities as scientific research institutions and qualified owners, systems and tools seem to be the most willing and able to implement TQM programs successfully and achieve the desired results, and e-learning has a role to play in achieving them.

- The evaluation process is at the heart of the TQM process in its three stages of development (inspection, statistical sampling, and organizational quality), which is incomplete unless there is an impact of e-learning. This process, because of the nature of university service and a focus on knowledge, will be more important and more difficult to measure and identify.
- The characteristics of universities and the nature of university work, in turn, impose challenges on the application of TQM (as well as when seeking ISO certification), and realize that the new world of knowledge is a digital world and it is necessary to take it seriously so that this application is not at the expense of traditions And the specificities of university work.
- The assessment process is the following gradual progression: routine procedure, self-assessment, overlap or participation with prestigious universities, regional accreditation, global university rankings and finally the international standard represented by the ten

universities in the rankings of world universities. While general accreditation by a specialized body in the country is the baseline for the assessment process.

SECOND: RECOMMENDATIONS

- Establishment of structures within institutions of higher education and scientific research shall be self-evaluated. , To be evaluated according to specific guidelines and criteria, based on the principles and formulas of quality and e-learning.
- The universities, which have not set a time plan to complete the evaluation structures at the level of all institutions of higher education and scientific research, should complete a specific period of time.
- Call for the establishment of integrated information infrastructure in universities and scientific research centers.
- Call upon the Arab League Educational, Cultural, Scientific and Arab Organization to adopt projects to disseminate information culture and digital knowledge.
- Focus on students and beneficiaries, from teachers, employees and society in general,
- Consider TQM as a key part of the university strategy, in general
- The need to recognize the seriousness of the role played by the electronic educator

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